

RHINOSINUSITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN: MODERN VIEWS ON PATHOGENESIS, CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS AND THERAPY

K.A. Ismatova¹, M.B. Odilova²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute^{1,2}

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Abstract. *Rhinosinusitis is one of the most common pathologies among the adult population, affecting from 5% to 15% of people, and among children - up to 5%. In recent years, there has been a steady increase in the incidence of rhinosinusitis, which is directly related to the increase in the number of cases of complicated pregnancy.*

Keywords: *rhinosinusitis, pregnant, complications, diagnostics.*

Introduction. Infectious diseases, including lesions of the paranasal sinuses, play an important role in the development of gestosis, antenatal and perinatal complications, which makes the study of this problem a relevant area of medical science [2]. Pregnancy is accompanied by profound hormonal and immune changes, which can lead to physiological immunodeficiency. This increases the woman's body's susceptibility to infections, including respiratory diseases. Rhinosinusitis in pregnant women often has an atypical course, with a tendency to a protracted process, reduced effectiveness of standard therapeutic regimens and a high risk of complications.

Despite significant advances in the study of rhinosinusitis, their pathogenesis, features of clinical manifestations and optimal treatment methods in pregnant women remain insufficiently studied. This article discusses modern views on the etiopathogenesis, clinical picture and therapy of rhinosinusitis in the gestational period.

Epidemiology of rhinosinusitis in pregnant women. According to local studies, acute rhinosinusitis is diagnosed in 10 million people annually in Russia. Similar trends are observed abroad:

- In Germany, over the past 10 years, the number of cases of acute and chronic rhinosinusitis ranges from 7 to 10 million annually.
- In the United States, about 16% of adults experience this disease annually.
- Over the past decade, the overall incidence of sinusitis has tripled, indicating an increase in infectious pathology of the upper respiratory tract [2,3].

Among pregnant women, the incidence of rhinosinusitis is also higher compared to the general population. Research shows that inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses are detected in 16.3% of pregnant women, which is twice the rate among non-pregnant women.

Pathogenesis of rhinosinusitis during pregnancy. Pregnancy is accompanied by a number of physiological changes that predispose to the development of rhinosinusitis:

1. Hormonal changes

a. An increase in the level of estrogen and progesterone leads to increased vascularization of the nasal mucosa, its swelling and hypersecretion of mucus.

b. These changes can cause nasal congestion and impair sinus drainage, creating favorable conditions for infection to develop.

2. Immunological adaptation: Predisposing factors for the development of rhinosinusitis during pregnancy are changes in the immune system, in particular, a shift towards the activation of Th2 lymphocytes, which is accompanied by increased humoral immunity and inhibition of the cellular component. This makes a pregnant woman's body extremely susceptible to viral and bacterial infections.

An imbalance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines can lead to disruption of an adequate immune response to an infectious agent, contributing to the latent course of the disease, its chronicity and increased risk of complications [4]. Insufficient activity of cellular immunity prevents the effective elimination of pathogens, which contributes to a protracted inflammatory process and the development of recurrent forms of rhinosinusitis [1].

3. Changes in physiological defense mechanisms:

a. Impaired mucociliary clearance due to changes in mucus viscosity and decreased activity of the ciliated epithelium aggravates the retention of pathogens in the nasal cavity and sinuses.

4. Free radical oxidation and antioxidant deficiency:

a. Pregnant women experience increased lipid peroxidation processes, which leads to damage to cell membranes and increased vascular permeability.

b. This promotes the development of inflammatory processes and impairs the recovery processes of the mucous membrane.

Clinical manifestations of rhinosinusitis in pregnant women. The clinical picture of rhinosinusitis in pregnant women has a number of features:

1. General symptoms:

1. Headache, feeling of pressure or fullness in the area of the affected sinuses [1,7].
2. Increased body temperature (more often with a bacterial infection).
3. General weakness, fatigue

2. Local manifestations:

1. Severe nasal congestion, often resistant to standard vasoconstrictor drugs.
2. Serous or purulent nasal discharge.
3. Pain in the forehead, cheeks, maxillary sinuses.
4. Increased pain when tilting the head forward.

3. Complicated forms:

1. Orbital complications: orbital phlegmon, periorbital edema.
2. Intracranial complications: meningitis, cavernous sinus thrombosis.
3. Spread of infection to the lower respiratory tract (bronchitis, pneumonia).

Diagnosis of rhinosinusitis in pregnant women:

1. Clinical methods

- Examination by an ENT doctor, rhinoscopy.
- Assessment of complaints and medical history.

2. Laboratory research:

- Complete blood count (increased leukocytes and ESR due to a bacterial process).
- Bacteriological culture of nasal secretions to identify the pathogen.

3. Instrumental methods:

- Ultrasound of the paranasal sinuses is a safe imaging method for pregnant women.
- Radiography – used to a limited extent, only in severe cases.

- MRI – preferred if complications are suspected.

Principles of treatment of rhinosinusitis during pregnancy

1. Non-drug methods

1. Rinse the nose with isotonic solutions (saline, aquamaris).
2. Inhalations with mineral water.
3. Humidify the air, drink plenty of fluids.

2. Drug treatment:

1. Antibiotics (for bacterial rhinosinusitis, strictly as prescribed by the doctor):
 - a. Penicillins (amoxicillin, amoxiclav) [5,6].
 - b. Cephalosporins (cephalexin, cefuroxime).
2. Mucolytics (ambroxol, carbocisteine - with caution).
3. Antiseptic drops (protargol, miramistin).
4. Decongestants (only local corticosteroids for severe cases - mometasone).
5. Protargol (colloidal silver) – reduces inflammation, reduces mucus secretion.

Prohibited during pregnancy:

1. Fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin) – have a teratogenic effect.
2. Aminoglycosides (gentamicin) are toxic to the fetus.
3. Tetracyclines (doxycycline) – cause malformations of bones and teeth.

3. Surgical treatment: In exceptional cases with the development of purulent complications (puncture of the maxillary sinus, endoscopic sanitation).

Conclusion. Rhinosinusitis in pregnant women is a significant problem that requires a special approach to diagnosis and treatment. Taking into account the immunological and hormonal characteristics of the gestational period, treatment should be as safe as possible, but at the same time effective. Further research is aimed at developing personalized therapeutic approaches that minimize risks to the mother and fetus.

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